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THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS FOR NON-FINANCIAL REPORTING PREPARATION REGARDING SOCIALLY RESPONSIBLE ACTIVITIES OF AN ENTERPRISE DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

ТЕОРЕТИКО-МЕТОДИЧНІ ОСНОВИ СКЛАДАННЯ НЕФІНАНСОВОЇ ЗВІТНОСТІ ЩОДО СОЦІАЛЬНО ВІДПОВІДАЛЬНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ ПІДПРИЄМСТВА В ПЕРІОД ПАНДЕМІЇ COVID-19

Svitlana V. Filyppova, DEcon, Professor
 Odessa Polytechnic State University, Odessa, Ukraine
 ORCID: 0000-0003-2245-3599
 Email: s.filyppova@gmail.com

Natalia M. Selivanova, PhD in Economics, Associate Professor
 Odessa Polytechnic State University, Odessa, Ukraine
 ORCID: 0000-0002-4157-4946
 Email: n.selivanova.odessa@gmail.com

Anastasiia V. Fraiman
 Odessa Polytechnic State University, Odessa, Ukraine
 ORCID: 0000-0003-3710-1385
 Email: fraymannastya1999@gmail.com

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Філіппова С.В., Селіванова Н.М., Фрайман А.В. Теоретико-методичні основи складання нефінансової звітності щодо соціально відповідальної діяльності підприємства в період пандемії COVID-19. Науково-методична стаття.

У даній статті досліджено теоретико-методичні основи складання нефінансової звітності щодо соціально відповідальної діяльності підприємства в період пандемії COVID-19. Узагальнено групи інструментів відносно рівня управління соціально-відповідальної діяльності підприємства. Визначено головні особливості та основні відмінності фінансової та нефінансової звітності. Сформовано основні інтереси та інформаційні потреби користувачів нефінансової звітності.

Висвітлено розроблені алгоритм складання нефінансової звітності та зміст її основних розділів в частині карантинних заходів підприємства в період пандемії COVID-19. Запропоновано форму щомісячного звіту для ведення управлінського обліку та витяг з Наказу про облікову політику про фактичні здійснені витрати соціально-відповідальної діяльності щодо проведення карантинних заходів.

Ключові слова: нефінансова звітність, соціально відповідальна діяльність, нормативно-правове забезпечення, управлінський облік, карантинні заходи

Filyppova S.V., Selivanova N.M., Fraiman A.V. Theoretical and Methodological Basis for Non-Financial Reporting Preparation regarding Socially Responsible Activities of an Enterprise during the COVID-19 Pandemic. Scientific and methodical article.

This article examines the theoretical and methodological basis for non-financial reporting preparation regarding socially responsible activities of an enterprise during the COVID-19 pandemic. The groups of tools concerning the management level of socially responsible activities of the enterprise are generalized. The main features and main differences of financial and non-financial reporting are identified.

The developed algorithm for compiling non-financial reporting and the content of its main sections in terms within quarantine measures of the enterprise during the COVID-19 pandemic are highlighted. The form of a monthly report for management accounting and an extract from the Order on Accounting Policy on the Actual Expenses of Socially Responsible Activities within quarantine activities are proposed.

Keywords: non-financial reporting, socially responsible activities, regulatory support, management accounting, quarantine measures

Conducting socially responsible activities of domestic enterprises raises the issue concerning theoretical and methodological foundations of non-financial reporting during the COVID-19 pandemic. This was due to the adaptation of many business entities to unusual conditions accompanied by applying the necessary measures aimed at preventing the spread of coronavirus. Anyway, the process of development, formation and implementation of non-financial reporting in terms of the quarantine measures was to improve the most effective development tool through which the enterprise was able to continuously continue its business, taking into account the necessary quarantine restrictions.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Such economists as K.V. Bezverkhyy, L.O. Voloshchuk, V.P. Kariev, I.S. Kovova, H.M. Liutova, V.V. Kirsanova, O.I. Malyshkin, N.M. Selivanova, S.M. Semenova, S.V. Filyppova, S.M. Shuliarenko and others devoted their research to the question of the essence and necessity of introduction of non-financial reporting of socially responsible enterprises.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

However, despite the widespread interest of many scholars in determining the nature of non-financial reporting as an effective tool of socially responsible enterprises, further research is needed on the aspects

of determining the effectiveness of its implementation during the COVID-19 pandemic, due to what the importance of non-financial reporting in the part of quarantine measures is considered today one of the urgent tasks among academic economists.

The aim of this article is to study the theoretical and methodological foundations of non-financial reporting on socially responsible activities of the enterprise during the COVID-19 pandemic and proposals on highlighting the algorithm of its compilation, summarizing the main sections, developing a monthly report form for management accounting and extract from the Order on accounting policy on the actual expenses incurred in carrying out quarantine measures.

The main part

The list of relevant tools concerning the socially responsible activities (SRA) management of the enterprise has become especially relevant over the last five years. The growth of social reporting in early 2019 was very significant, but the global COVID-19 pandemic somewhat suspended the domestic enterprises activity in this direction. The reason for this were the quarantine restrictions during the economic activity of enterprises, because in such

conditions their response to the current situation was extremely slow than usual. In addition, the great privilege of many business entities was the high level of their financial position which, in turn, helped to neutralize possible risks during the quarantine conditions.

Nevertheless, in order to increase the enterprise reputation and investment attractiveness, the necessary stakeholders' attraction, or increase the level of trust of existing ones, business entities continue to use management tools such as ethics codes and non-financial (social) reports, etc. Applying these tools helps to reduce existing expenses and increase the business entity capitalization, as well as the optimal systematization of information data, the correct organization of which helps to make important management decisions on the quarantine measures.

Let's reflect the main tools of the enterprise SRA management (Table 1) with subsequent grouping into strategic, tactical and operational groups in order to consider in detail the characteristics of each of the elements, the use of which will help to report on the enterprise SRA, taking into account the current quarantine conditions.

Table 1. The Groups of Tools regarding the Management Level of the Enterprise SRA in the Quarantine Conditions

The Tools Group	The Tools List
Strategic	Corporate ethics code - regulates relationships with business entities by adhering to moral principles and norms.
	Corporate management code – regulates the relationship with the environment on the basis of these general provisions; in addition, pays considerable attention to the ethical standards of conduct the enterprise employees.
	Stakeholders map – helps to identify parties concerned and determine whether they have an impact on the activities of the enterprise or are under such influence.
	Social investments are based on ethical and moral norms which provide for the investment of financial, material, technological, managerial resources with a reliable prospect for the further development of the enterprise.
	Social programmes contain the main goal, the necessary tasks which will be used to disseminate to all the possible stakeholders.
Tactical	Preparing non-financial report – helps the enterprise to find all possible non-financial risks that arise during economic operations and provide a detailed assessment of the possibility to eliminate them.
	Ethics committees – address important issues of corporate ethics in developing a strategy for the enterprise development in this area.
	Ethical examinations – establish the conformity of the enterprise activities with ethical standards by comprehensive analysis.
Operational	Cause marketing – focuses on the donation of part of the enterprise income, which was received at the end of the reporting period, and is usually directed in favour of the charity mission.
	Social communications – are reproduced by exchanging views between actors on the emergence of specific situations in the business environment.
	Ethics maps development – improves ethics codes by clarifying ethical rules and recommendations for each employee of the enterprise.
	Social audits – are aimed at collecting information on the social impact and programmes of the enterprise in order to provide a more accurate assessment and report.
	Non-financial reporting – increases the company transparency, strengthens business relations in the field of business, builds trust in the enterprise not only partners, investors (stakeholders), but also consumers / customers.

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1].

In addition to grouping tools relative to the management level of the enterprise, there is a general grouping relative to the enterprise, i.e. on internal and external tools. According to the table 1 the internal tools include ethics codes and ethics maps. In turn, the external tools will include social audits, examinations

and investment. Thus, the internal tools of the enterprise SRA will concern only the management and employees of the enterprise, and external will affect the state, stakeholders (e.g. partners or investors) and consumers.

Taking into account the pandemic conditions which has lasted for more than a year, introducing the non-financial reporting at the enterprise has become quite relevant in Ukraine among all possible management tools mentioned above. The fact is that despite COVID-19 stakeholders continue to be interested in the economic situation of many enterprises, that is why high-quality and true non-financial reporting is a key to success, which means the appropriate investment which will help not only to

financially support the enterprise SRA, but also to maintain competitiveness on the market in the quarantine conditions.

Many questions arise as to whether non-financial reporting can be considered a separate element from the financial one. In order to do this, it is necessary to identify in more detail the main features and differences of these types of reporting. Let's display in the table 2 the main criteria by which we compare financial and non-financial reporting.

Table 2. Peculiarities and Main Differences of Financial and Non-Financial Reporting

Index	Financial Reporting	Non-Financial Reporting
Mandatory reporting	Required	Voluntary /required
The reporting purpose	Providing information on the financial position, the results of operations and cash flows of the enterprise	Providing information about the enterprise SRA
The information users	External and internal	
Normative regulation	National accounting regulations (standards)	Methodological recommendations for compiling the management report № 982, International Standards
Data openness	Restricted	Full
Subject matter	Economic results	Economic, environmental and social results
Temporal orientation	Assessing of the past	Assessing the past and predicting the future
Using measures	The only monetary measure	Different measures and quality characteristics

Source: authors' own development

From the table 2 we can see that the only common feature between financial and non-financial reporting is the list of information users: internal and external. However, it is important to note that non-financial reporting can significantly complement economic indicators in financial reporting with the environmental and social ones. In addition, non-financial reporting uses various measures that detail business activities, as well as separate sections that focus on important and necessary tasks for the future. Such combinations lead to providing the sufficient information about the socio-economic activities of the enterprise as a whole, which helps to increase the

level of openness and transparency of the business entity for parties concerned.

The information needs of external and internal users of non-financial reporting deserve special consideration. In this case, it is important to note what exactly the information need is trying to get the user from the content of non-financial reporting, whether consideration of this type of reporting is considered effective both for internal and external users, and what benefits they have from it. Let's pay attention to the table 3 which groups users of non-financial reporting and their information needs, taking into account the quarantine conditions.

Table 3. Interests and Information Needs of the Non-Financial Reporting Users in the Quarantine Conditions

Users' Group of Non-Financial Reporting	Users' Interest and Information Need in the Quarantine Conditions
1	2
Potential investors, creditors, partners	Both potential investors and creditors need information about the current state of the company. This is due to the fact that they need to understand whether it is appropriate to invest in the enterprise SRA projects, so they are interested in obtaining information on the solvency and liquidity of the business entity. It is advisable to include potential partners in this list, because for them the social aspects that should be reflected in the non-financial report allow to assess all possible risks. However, each of this group of users in the quarantine conditions, first of all, will be interested in how the enterprise withstood such non-standard working conditions, how strongly the SRA on the quarantine measures affected the financial results, whether the entity really behaved during the pandemic as a company that conducts SRA, whether it should be invested further.
Owners, managers and employees of the enterprise	As a rule, the enterprise owners and managers are mostly interested in information about the activities profitability, i.e. about incomes, expenses and financial results. However, taking into account the trends of the last five years, the social aspects highlighted in the non-financial report. push management to make many managerial decisions, and the quarantine conditions that haunt most domestic enterprises for more than a year are not left out, so information on the results of social activity will help in the future to rationally determine the following social tasks, in our case compliance with the quarantine measures to be performed by a socially responsible enterprise. As for employees, this category of society is no less interested in obtaining information about the social role of their work, namely safety and health during the pandemic, the coverage of which remains one of the components of the non-financial report.

Continuation of Table 3

1	2
Buyers and customers, suppliers and contractors	Any supplier and contractor is interested in the enterprise being able to pay in advance for the goods and services provided. However, taking into account the conditions prevailing during the global quarantine introduction, non-financial reporting, namely the economic combination of indicators with social aspects, will help them to make sure of this. Buyers and customers also have the greatest benefit of covering the non-financial report, because they must understand whether they receive services safely in the conditions of the quarantine. The more the business entity will report socially to its own customers, the more revenue it will receive, of course, not in the usual marketing, but in fact the enterprise SRA.
State bodies (government agencies)	Usually, if owners and managers are interested in preserving their own profit in extreme conditions, the state bodies focus their attention during the pandemic on compliance with all the quarantine measures, especially for utilities, which are given the appropriate orders concerning rules of conduct of economic activity during quarantine. Within this context, in the non-financial report, they will mostly be interested in whether the employees' working conditions are safely organized, especially the conditions for the services provision, because this procedure also involves the enterprise consumers, who should not be exposed to the potential danger of a pandemic expansion.
Society (public)	Probably, the content of the non-financial report in the quarantine conditions is considered to be the most appropriate for the society, because the public usually appreciates the information about the impact of the enterprise on the society as a whole. Many aspects of this report will need to be reflected here: how the enterprise organizes quarantine measures during the pandemic for employees and consumers, how many individual protection means were purchased and issued, how often the office premises and public transport were disinfected, what additional benefits were given to employees and for what purpose, whether charitable activities were carried out to avoid the spread of the pandemic and how much money was spent on these activities.

Source: compiled by authors on materials [2].

As we can see from the table 3, despite the fact that non-financial reporting is defined as the main effective tool of the enterprise SRA, which contains information about economic and social activities in the quarantine conditions, each user needs to consider the relevant aspect, i.e. interested in providing especially important for him information.

Thus, in a broad sense, non-financial reporting is a tool for the enterprise, which displays the main indicators of economic and social responsibility, and the results of which allow the business entity owner to reproduce the real picture of successful or unsuccessful functioning of the enterprise, which further determines the necessary tasks development, aimed at improving the efficiency of economic activity during quarantine.

Appropriate adjustments have recently been made to national legislation which is true only for large and medium-sized enterprises, as well as the enterprises of public interest. According to the Law of Ukraine "On Accounting and Financial Reporting" [3] introduced a new element of reporting, i.e. management report, which must contain both financial and non-financial information, and must be published annually.

Thus, in accordance with the methodological recommendations for the management report preparation, which came into force on 7 December 2018 [4], the content of the report should be formed in particular in such areas as economic activity,

environmental aspects, social aspects and personnel policy, and also corporate management. Thus, the first mandatory reports began to be published in late 2018 but the coronavirus pandemic, which broke out unexpectedly, "postponed" the date of publication until the end of 2020. Taking into account the given emergencies, the trend of development and implementation of non-financial reporting has changed somewhat, in contrast to the legislation. After all, the content of National Methodological Recommendations is given in a very narrow sense, and even despite the general guidelines, there are no clear guidelines for this report development.

Due to the fact that domestic legislation regulates the necessary rules for non-financial reporting mostly in the narrow sense, enterprises have the opportunity to use international regulations, which provide coverage of the enterprise SRA, given the current quarantine conditions, adaptation to which somewhat complicates the main economic and social indicators.

For the most part, international regulatory instruments regulate the most important basic requirements to be met by social enterprises. In addition, the necessity to maintain non-financial reporting, which is able to show not only the successful operation of the business entity, but also a list of the tasks set and performed concerning the enterprise SRA and quarantine measures, will be discussed in more detail in the Table 4.

Table 4. Regulatory Support for the Non-Financial Reporting Preparation for the enterprise SRA the in Quarantine Conditions

Regulatory Instrument	The Content Disclosure
1	2
Social Accountability 8000	The standard covers the most important, and most importantly accepted by society, the necessary systems of employees' work organization in the enterprise, which primarily relate to their social protection, namely safe working conditions. Thus, the standard groups the rules, compliance with which should be covered in the non-financial report which applies not only to the employer but also to its employees.

Continuation of Table 4

1	2
Account Ability 1000	The standard is aimed at the development, formation, preparation and wide dissemination of quality non-financial reporting in order to fully interest potential stakeholders, the presence of which in the future may increase the level of successful operation of the enterprise through the successful investment. This standardized document contains simple, relevant and practical information on high-quality involvement of stakeholders, i.e. provides a combination of social aspects of the enterprise in the overall business organization.
Global Reporting Initiative	The GRI standard is considered to be one of the most common standards, which is very popular among enterprises, because it contains a set of various criteria by which one can generate a single report on the economic, environmental and social performance of the enterprise. The content of this document provides an opportunity to delve into various aspects of the enterprise SRA: from the fight against corruption and environmental protection, and ending with the protection of its own employees in unpredictable conditions.

Source: compiled by authors on materials [5-7].

This list, shown in the table 4 includes well-known standards among domestic and international enterprises that can be applied when preparing non-financial reporting in the quarantine conditions. The GRI standard is very popular, because it contains all aspects of the enterprise SRA, the coverage of which helps to increase its competitiveness.

The AA1000 standard is considered to be no less popular, as it also contains the above-mentioned aspects, combining reflections of indicators that will promote the relations development with stakeholders.

As for the SA8000 standard, its content is based on international legislation on a person's safe working conditions. In this case, social responsibility is highlighted in a more narrow sense, since it is focused on the relations between employers and employees.

In addition, the development and further preparation of non-financial reporting plays an important role in the company not only in the quarantine conditions, because the presence of such reporting has a positive impact on the brand formation, and also attracts investors who are willing to invest heavily in the of this enterprise development.

Before deciding on the implementation of non-financial reporting, it should be understood that in practice there are different forms of its presentation, namely: arbitrary reporting form, comprehensive and standardized reports [8].

The simplest form is arbitrary reporting because it informs external users and is not auditable. However, it is difficult to call it effective, as its use is due to the lack of the enterprise's transparency. In turn, comprehensive reports are considered more effective. They differ from arbitrary reports in that they must cover information about the enterprise activities in three different areas: economic, environmental and social.

However, the most popular are standardized reports, as they have most advantages over other types, the main of which is the possibility of the report's comparability of different enterprises. It is also considered to be generally accepted and officially recognized in the international community, as it reflects the most important aspects of the enterprise SRA and is formed on a set of the internal and external reporting [9].

Due to the fact that the stakeholders' interests, even during the COVID-19 pandemic, are an

important goal for any enterprise, it is necessary to determine the sections and divisions that will be covered in the non-financial report of the enterprise.

Let's display in the Figure 1 the names of the main sections and subsections, as well as a list of indicators for quarantine measures, the coverage of which in the non-financial report will be of interest to external users.

With the help shown in the Figure 1 indicators systematization, it is possible to identify the competitive advantages of the enterprise, which will significantly increase the rating and interest of stakeholders, as the business entity officially informs the public about all its socially responsible actions concerning the quarantine measures.

Indeed, in the context of comprehensive indicators of social security in the information system of the enterprise, which is covered in the close relationship of social accounting with financial, management and tax accounting, the introduction and further improvement of accounting for SRA in the enterprise in modern conditions is an urgent issue for every chief accountant. This is primarily due to the fact that all non-financial reporting data should be publicly available to owners, managers, potential investors, creditors, partners, state bodies, which will significantly affect the reform of information support for all possible stakeholders.

Of course, it is quite difficult to outline the economic benefits of running SRA, in this connection, non-financial reporting and is the main and effective tool of informing stakeholders about the enterprise SRA. After all, due to the meaningful and clear formation of the social report it is possible to reflect all socially responsible actions of the enterprise in the COVID-19 pandemic conditions.

Thus, the business entity will not only be able to assess the effectiveness of its own activities, but also increase the goodwill level of the enterprise which, in turn, will create a favourable environment in the interest of potential stakeholders and consumers of services. First of all, let's offer in the Figure 2 the algorithm for the formation of non-financial reporting for the enterprise, taking into account the fact that the preparation of this report will be displayed in any form in order to highlight the most important information about the enterprise SRA concerning the quarantine measures.

Figure 1. Indicators Presentation on Quarantine Measures in the Non-Financial Reporting of the Enterprise
 Source: authors' own development

Figure 2. The Algorithm for Compiling Non-Financial Reporting on SRA in Terms of Quarantine Measures of the Enterprise
 Source: authors' own development

Thus, we will divide the processes of development, formation and implementation into three main stages: initial, reporting stage and final. Each of them will be characterized by the list of consecutive actions required for an effective mechanism for compiling non-financial reporting.

Accordingly, from the Figure 2 it can be seen that the process of development, formation and implementation of non-financial reporting is quite time consuming and requires considerable effort from employees responsible for its preparation. Nevertheless, if one consistently follows the stages of

the algorithm, clearly performs the set tasks, the business entity is able to obtain a powerful and effective tool for its successful operation.

One of the most important steps for the enterprise will be to determine the main indicators that should be covered in the non-financial report on the SRA concerning the quarantine measures. Thus, the main task for the enterprise is to adequately substantiate the main sections that will be reflected in social reporting in order to quickly find the necessary information data for any group of stakeholders. Let's reflect them in the table 5.

Table 5. The Recommended Content of the Main sections of Non-Financial Reporting on SRA in terms of the Quarantine Measures of the Enterprise during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Section 1	Contents of the Proposed Sections for the Non-Financial Report 2
The management opening speech	Determining the activities of the enterprise and prospects for development.
Information about the enterprise in the conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic	Carrying out quarantine conditions, as a result of which the business entity has shown itself in the SRA.
The enterprise strategy during the quarantine restrictions	Displaying the main goal and setting tasks for the necessary quarantine measures during the pandemic period.
Stability of consumer demand for the purchase of finished products (goods, works, services)	Monitoring changes in consumer demand for the purchase of finished products (goods, works, services), taking into account quarantine restrictions.
Economic performance activities in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic	Grouping the financial results of the enterprise, which deteriorated due to increased costs incurred for carrying out of important socially significant quarantine measures.
Creation of the corresponding commission at the enterprise	Displaying prerequisites for creation of the corresponding commission and statement of the basic tasks which have been discussed by its representatives concerning features and conditions of conducting economic activity during quarantine.
Purchasing personal protective equipment:	Compliance with the DSTU requirements regarding the purchase of quality goods that meet all established standards, the availability of supporting documents.
-the number of purchased PPE;	Displaying the total number of purchased PPE, as well as depending on their purpose, i.e. the division of PPE into separate categories.
-the amount of costs for the purchase of PPE	Determining the total amount of costs associated with the purchase of PPE.
Basic quarantine measures for employees:	Forming the list of necessary measures during the quarantine restrictions, the importance and significance for their implementation.
-distribution of personal protective equipment;	Displaying the number of PPE distributed to employees of all departments.
-carrying out disinfection measures;	Creating safe working conditions for employees through disinfection in administrative and other premises of the enterprise.
-organization of PCR testing and other medical support.	Providing employees with medical services, which have been manifested in the purchase of rapid express tests for the diagnosis of COVID-19 for PCR testing among the employees in the face of deteriorating epidemic situation.
The percentage of funds for medical care in staff costs	Displaying a clear example of the component of the funds amount allocated for both medical care and the creation of safe working conditions for employees, in the total expenses (in the form of pie charts).
Percentage of funds for labour protection and safety in the total costs of labour protection	
Basic quarantine measures for consumers:	Forming a list of necessary measures during the quarantine restrictions for the main consumers of the enterprise during a pandemic.
-providing of personal protective equipment;	Displaying the number of PPE used by consumers when receiving finished products (goods, works, and services).
-carrying out disinfection measures.	Fulfilment of conditions of the organization for carrying out the disinfection actions (place of carrying out disinfections, frequency of carrying out disinfections a day, the procedure of carrying out disinfection).
The percentage of funds for the safe conditions organization when providing consumers with finished products (goods, works, services) in the costs for labour protection	Displaying a clear example of the component of the funds amount allocated for creating safe conditions for the main consumers of the enterprise, in the total cost (in the form of a pie chart).
Costs for quarantine measures depending on the type of activity:	Determining the total expenses of quarantine measures for both employees and consumers, in particular the expenses distribution for:
-costs for quarantine measures of the main activity;	-providing the employees' health care;
-production overhead expenses for quarantine measures;	-providing the employees' health care; -carrying out disinfection measures; -utilization of used PPE.

Continuation of Table 5

1	2
-administrative expenses for the quarantine measures;	-providing the employees' health care; -disinfection of administrative premises.
-Expenses for loss on quarantine measures;	-providing major consumers' health care;
-other operating expenses for the quarantine measures.	-the employees' medical support; -providing the employees' transportation; -providing housing for the employees; -carrying out charitable activities.
PPE disposal expenses	Using PPE disposal services through a third party organization involvement, determining the expenses amount of this event.
Relationship and impact of social indicators on the financial condition of the enterprise	Implementation of spending for the enterprise SRA and its impact on the deterioration of the financial position of the business entity, but socially important impact on creating safe conditions for employees and consumers of the enterprise.
Participation in charity events	Displaying information on participation in promotional activities aimed at preventing the spread of COVID-19.
General conclusions	Substantiation of the role the of enterprise SRA for the society, its achievement and adaptation to quarantine restrictions.
Appendices	Displaying the main quarantine measures of the business entity in the form of histograms, graphs, circular diagrams and other kinds of graphical representation with the purpose of interest of all possible groups of stakeholders.

Source: authors' own development

As it can be seen from the table 5, there are many options for including in the non-financial report sections that will characterize the SRA in terms of the quarantine measures, and even this list is not exhaustive, as reporting in this format requires some special content. For example, different measures and the qualitative characteristics should be used in the report, while highlighting the information data of a social nature. In order for non-financial reporting to attract the attention of different groups of stakeholders, it is important not only to create a bright report, but also to select information that will cover the enterprise SRA as best as possible.

It should be noted that the selecting the system of indicators in non-financial reporting is quite a time-consuming process, because during it the employees responsible for compiling the report should justify the choice of information to cover the enterprise SRA. Of course, this process can be carried out by an appointed group of employees, but it is worth noting that the basis of reporting to the business entity to carry out the quarantine measures, first of all, should be formed in the management accounting system.

At any enterprise that wants to report officially to the population, consumers, potential investors and controlling bodies, a management unit should be established, which will be responsible for recording information in monetary and natural dimension, which will detail the enterprise SRA and significantly

increase the efficiency level of managerial decisions making.

In this regard, we propose a developed form of a monthly report, which will be provided for management accounting of actual expenses of the SRA in terms of the quarantine measures (the table 6). This report will further serve as an effective source of information for non-financial reporting formation. After all, management accounting is first of all very closely related to social reporting, with the help of its maintenance information is displayed that is useful for different groups of stakeholders.

As it can be seen from the table 6, the form of a monthly report on the actual expenses of the enterprise SRA should include a list of quarantine measures and recording the expenses incurred by the business entity as a result of creating safe working conditions for its own employees and consumers. It is proposed to submit the monthly report form in a consolidated form with a weekly breakdown. This is due to the fact that the data for the month may be too generalized, and therefore uninformative nature of the grouped data. In addition, a column "Notes" can be added to the report, in which a manager will be able to provide important information about a significant change in the expenses of any quarantine measure. Thus, the data calculated by the management unit can be immediately included in the non-financial report, which will simplify the process of forming non-financial statements.

Table 6. The Form of a Monthly Report for Management Accounting of the Actual Costs Incurred by SRA concerning Quarantine Activities at the Enterprise

The list of quarantine measures	The amount of actual expenses for «...», UAH.				Total amount of expenses, UAH.	The responsible person	Deadline
	I week	II week	III week	IV week			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Providing PPE to employees:							
- main production unit;							
- general production unit;							
- management unit;							

Continuation of Table 6

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
- sales unit;							
-other units.							
Providing PPE to consumers							
Carrying out disinfection measures in office and other premises							
Providing employees with remedies:							
<...> (depending on the units)							
Organization of PCR testing for employees:							
<...> (depending on the units)							
Organization of employees' vaccination:							
<...> (depending on the units)							
Employees transportation:							
<...> (depending on the units)							
Providing housing for employees:							
<...> (depending on the units)							
Disposal of used PPE							
Charitable activity							
Total						X	X

Source: authors' own development

In addition, it will be important to identify a responsible person who will oversee the development and formation of non-financial reporting. As a rule, such a person is the chief accountant of the enterprise, because it is he/she who accumulates the necessary information that should be reflected in the report. It should also be noted that this type of reporting should

be done once a year. In order to officially and normatively support social reporting, it is necessary to record this in the Order on Accounting Policy (Figure 3), highlighting the sub-item of non-financial reporting on SRA in terms of the quarantine measures.

<p>ORDER on the Accounting Policy of the Enterprise <.....> Non-financial reporting on Socially Responsible Activities in Terms of Quarantine Measures <.....></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. When preparing non-financial reporting, follow the Methodological Recommendations for Preparing a Management Report, approved by the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine № 982 dated 7 December 2018. 2. When complying non-financial reporting, use the form developed by the management unit, which is approved by the head of the enterprise and fixed in the appendix to the Order on Accounting Policy. 3. Non-financial reporting should include economic indicators directly related to socially responsible quarantine measures. 4. To form non-financial reporting based on the results of each year in the form of an annual report. 5. For publishing non-financial reporting, the deadlines are set by 1 March of each current year. 6. Responsibility for the process of development and formation of non-financial reporting should be put on the chief accountant.

Figure 3. Extract from the Order on the Accounting Policy for Non-Financial Reporting on SRA in terms of the Quarantine Measures of the Enterprise

Source: authors' own development

Therefore, the most important points regarding the application of relevant regulatory tools during the non-financial reporting preparation, choosing its form, determining the features of its content, the preparation period, publication and appointment of the responsible person (Figure 3) must be covered in the internal disposition document, i.e. Accounting Policy Orders that will ensure a proper social reporting process.

Conclusions

Thus, non-financial reporting has become especially relevant in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, because the coverage of its social indicators requires the enterprise to make important managerial decisions on the quarantine measures. Thus, non-financial reporting has some differences

from financial one: the mandatory introduction of it depends on whether the enterprise is in the public interest, and its subject component, although it contains a set of economic indicators, but in combination with social ones. In addition, each user of non-financial reporting has one's own information needs, depending on what the stakeholder is most interested in the quarantine conditions. As for the normative regulation of the reporting, the content of the Methodological Recommendations for Preparing a Management Report is provided in general, as there are no clear instructions on the reporting form development. Particular attention should be paid to international standards, the use of which by domestic enterprises is appropriate during the coronavirus pandemic. In this regard, the developed

recommendations for non-financial reporting implementation on SRA in terms of quarantine measures will allow the enterprise to openly and transparently inform all possible groups of stakeholders about their social activities, which, in turn, will increase the reputation and investment

attractiveness of the business entity. In addition, the successful arrangement of non-financial indicators in the report will help to make sound and informed managerial decisions during the COVID-19 pandemic which will help to improve the efficiency of economic activities even during the quarantine.

Abstract

Conducting socially responsible activities of domestic enterprises raises the issue of theoretical and methodological foundations of non-financial reporting during the COVID-19 pandemic. This is due to the adaptation of many businesses to unusual conditions, accompanied by the application of the necessary measures to prevent the spread of coronavirus. One way or another, the process of development, formation and implementation of non-financial reporting in terms of quarantine measures was to improve the most effective development tool through which the enterprise was able to continuously continue its business taking into account the necessary quarantine restrictions. Therefore, the aim of this article is to study the theoretical and methodological foundations of non-financial reporting on socially responsible activities of the enterprise during the COVID-19 pandemic and proposals to highlight the algorithm of its compilation, summarize the main sections, develop a monthly report form for management accounting and extract from the Order on Accounting Policy on the Actual Expenses incurred in carrying out quarantine measures. As it is known, despite COVID-19, the stakeholders continue to be interested in the economic situation of many enterprises, so high-quality and truthful non-financial reporting is the key to success which means appropriate investment that will help maintain market competitiveness during the quarantine. Due to the fact that meeting the stakeholders' interests, even during the coronavirus pandemic, is an important goal for any business, it is necessary to identify the sections and units that will be covered in the non-financial report of the enterprise. Of course, the process of developing, compiling and implementing non-financial reporting is quite time consuming and requires a lot of effort from the employees responsible. Nevertheless, if you consistently follow the stages of a certain algorithm, clearly perform the tasks set before you, the business entity is able to obtain a powerful and effective tool for its successful operation. In addition, at any enterprise that wants to report officially to the population, consumers, potential investors and controlling bodies, a management unit should be established, which will be responsible for recording information in monetary and natural dimension, which will detail the enterprise SRA and significantly increase the efficient level of managerial decisions making. In this regard, it is advisable to develop a form of monthly report, which will be provided for management accounting of the actual expenses of the SRA in terms of the quarantine. Thus, non-financial reporting has become especially relevant in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, as the coverage of its social indicators requires the enterprise to make important managerial decisions regarding the quarantine measures. In this regard, the developed recommendations for the implementation of a form of non-financial reporting on SRA in terms of the quarantine measures will allow the enterprise to openly and transparently inform all possible groups of stakeholders about its own social activities.

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